

On Delignification of Jute Fibre.

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Investigations to improve the textile quality of bast fibres by the removal of incrusting matters have so long been limited mainly to flax and hemp which are endowed by nature with comparatively long ultimate fibres or cells. The usual methods of removing the lignone matter disintegrate the fibres into ultimate cells (which must be at least 15-20 mm. long to be of value for textile purposes) and cannot therefore be applied to jute. The following experiments were undertaken with the object of delignifying jute, one of the most important crops in Bengal, without reducing it to ultimate fibres and thus extending its usefulness not only as a textile fibre, but also, if delignification can be carried to a sufficient extent, as raw material for various cellulose industries. The textile quality of these treated fibres could however be determined only by actual spinning tests and an exhaustive investigation of their physical properties.

Owing to the secrecy maintained by manufacturers, a review of the methods for the "cottonisation" of flax and hemp cannot be undertaken in this place. It is believed however that most of these processes employ halogens, either in the free state or in chemical combination (Waentig, *Z. ang. Chem.*, 1926, 59, 1237) or caustic soda of suitable concentration at a high temperature (Waentig, *ibid.*, 1923, 56, 129) as delignifying agent. The application of the above reagents, as also that of the sulphite liquor of paper technologists is too drastic for jute, reducing it to ultimate fibres. The recent process of Cross and Engelstad (*E.P.* 12945, 1922) of treatment with 6-7% aqueous sulphur dioxide also reduces jute to ultimate fibres (Cross and Engelstad, *J. Soc. Chem. Ind.*, 1924, p. 256T). It is evident that a less drastic action must be chosen in view of the peculiar chemical and physical constitution of jute.

Chemically, jute belongs to a class of substances known as lignocelluloses. According to Cross and Bevan ("Cellulose," 1918, p. 94) jute consists of cellulose and noncellulose or lignone complexes. The cellulose complex is made up of α -cellulose and β -cellulose,

while the lignone complex contains a diketo-R-hexene group coupled to a hydroprone group and an aldehydic side-chain similar to that of cinnamic aldehyde (Cross and Doree, "Researches on Cellulose," IV, pp. 156 and 163; also Cross and Engelstad, *Chem. and Ind.*, 1924, p. 254). From a study of the chemical and physiological properties of jute, they conclude that jute is a chemically homogeneous complex. This view is however contradicted by different investigators (Lehne and Schepmann, *Z. ang. Chem.*, 1925, 58, 97) who maintain that in the so called lignocelluloses, the cellulose fibre is merely incrustated with lignone matter. Wislicenus, on the other hand, finds in lignocelluloses an example of adsorption between colloids, the cellulose and lignone complexes being held together by the forces of surface energy. This view is supported by the microscopical observations of Robinson (*Trans. Roy. Soc.*, 1920, B 210, 49).

Physically, jute consists of a bundle of fibres, held together by incrusting matter, the individual fibre being made up of a large number of cells or ultimate fibres, arranged like a telescope and cemented with one another by means of minute quantities of amorphous substances whose chemical nature however remains unknown. These ultimate fibres are again made up of a large number of parallel "fibrills," whose axes may or may not lie in the direction of the cell, these "fibrills" being again made up of the combination of a number of parallel chain of crystals (Herzog, *Zeit. ang. Chem.*, 1926, 59, 299). In any chemical treatment of the fibre it is therefore necessary that this cementing matter should remain as far as possible unaffected and thus prevent the progressive disintegration of the fibre. This is evidently not the case in the usual methods of delignification. Further, owing to the susceptibility of cellulose to the action of strong acids and alkalis, their use has to be avoided. As a milder reagent, treatment with aqueous solution of neutral sodium sulphite (Keebra process) under great pressure suggest itself, but under these conditions, water hydrolyses the fibre. We have therefore turned to mildly acidic phenols as a suitable solvent for the lignone complex.

The solubility of lignone matter in phenol was first observed by Bühler (D.R.P. 94467, 1897; *Zeit. Ang. Chem.*, 1898, 11, 119). A similar patent was taken by Kalb & Schöller in 1920 (D.R.P. 365287), while the influence of hydrochloric acid as a catalyser was observed by Hartmuth (D.R.P. 326705 and 328783, 1919). Special mention

may be made of the work of Hillmer (*Cellulose-chemie*, 1925, 6, 169) who investigated the action of polyhydroxy and substituted phenols on lignone separated by Wilstätter's method and also on wood meal. He found that polyhydroxy phenols were good solvents for lignone and that iodine acted as a better catalyser than hydrochloric acid. But the effect of the solvents on the structure of the fibre or their action on the lignone or cellulose complex in ligno-celluloses was not investigated. Cross and Doree on the other hand found that a compound of jute with phlorogucinol was highly resistant to the action of 42% hydrochloric acid and was presumably a homogeneous chemical substance, the lignone complex being unlikely to be separated from cellulose by the use of solvents ("Cellulose Researches," IV, p. 169). It was therefore necessary to investigate if incrusting matters of jute could actually be removed by treatment with phenols.

Solvent Action of Phenols.

A few preliminary experiments with excess of phenol, resorcinol, *m*- and *p*-cresols and creosote showed that the lignone complex of jute was more or less removed by all these reagents at their boiling temperatures. In the selection of the solvent, care has to be taken that it should have the least possible effect on the cellulose constituent. On treating cellulose (quantitative filter paper) with creosote at high temperature and under pressure (Exp. 9, Table I b) it was found that the loss in the weight of cellulose amounted to only 1 per cent.

This led to the adoption of creosote as a suitable solvent, beechwood creosote (Merck) having been used for the purpose of these investigations.

It has to be understood however that the mechanism of solution is by no means a purely physical one. Cross and Doree ("Cellulose Researches," IV, p. 160) observe that chemical action takes place between lignone and phenols, the compounds being extremely stable. Hillmer (*Cellulose-chemie*, 1925, 6, 180) explains the stability by assuming a condensation product with a ring formation. This lignone-phenol derivative apparently dissolves in excess of the solvent.

Prevention of Disintegration into Ultimate Fibres.

While treating jute with creosote or with other phenols in the autoclave, it was found that the fibre became very brittle. This was obviously due to the acidic nature of the phenols, converting the

cellulose into hydrocellulose. The addition of the basic substances had the desired effect in preventing the disintegration.

It will be observed from the following table that maximum effect is obtained by mixing creosote with 10% of its volume of pyridine (Exp. 4). The reduction in the weight of the fibre by the use of larger amount of pyridine is mainly due to the attack on cellulose. It will also be noted (Expt. 6, Table Ia) that when jute is treated with pyridine alone, the reduction in weight of the fibre amounts to 20%, of this only 9.69% being due to the removal of lignone (taking 19.69% as the lignone content of raw jute), the remaining 10.31% being apparently removed from the cellulose complex. It is to be noted that neither the structure nor the tensile strength of jute seriously suffers from this treatment, the cementing matter remaining practically unaffected. Hillmer (*loc. cit.*, p. 183) observed that addition of pyridine serves to lower the solubility of cellulose in phenols. In contrast with this observation, it is found that pyridine attacks the cellulose complex, though the structure of the fibre is not thereby affected. When pyridine is substituted by aqueous ammonia, the fibre-strength is considerably reduced, due to the hydrolytic action of water.

Investigations into the hydrolysis of the fibre by water showed that at 100°, the fibre was very little affected. But at 193-195°, the loss in weight was considerable, and the fibre was reduced to pulp. In treating the fibre at high temperature, the use of water was therefore avoided, and rectified spirit was used in exerting pressure in the autoclave.

TABLE I.

Effect of the addition of basic substances.

Temperature 193-195°; Pressure 28-30 atmospheres.

Time of treatment 4 hours.

Solvent 50 c.c. creosote for 1 gm. of jute.

Expt.	Basic subst.	% Basic subst. in solvent.	Loss in wt. of jute %	Lignin present %	Methyl no.	Tensile strength.
1	Pyridine	60	30.06	...	3.5	...
2	..	40	25.6	3.8
3	..	20	24.4	4.2	3.5	Good
4	..	10	23.0	4.4	3.8	Good
5	..	0	17.4	6.5	4.73	Bad

TABLE I(a).

Expt.	Basic subst.	C.c. of basic subst. to 1 gm. of jute.	Loss in wt. of jute %	Lignin present. %	Tensile strength.
6	Pyridine (no creosote)	80	20.4	10	Good
7	Aqueous ammonia	2	17.6	5.4	Bad
8	Aniline	2	16.4

The effect of the addition of pyridine on cellulose will be clearly seen from the following data obtained by the action of creosote and creosote-pyridine on quantitative filter paper (cellulose).

TABLE I(b).

Effect of the addition of pyridine on cellulose.

Temperature 193-195°; Pressure 28-30 atmos.

Time of treatment 4 hours.

Expt.	Vol. of creosote to 1 gm. of jute.	Vol. of pyridine added to creosote.	Loss in weight %	Strength of paper.
9	100 c.c.	nil	1	Brittle
10	100 c.c.	30 c.c.	21.8	Fair.

Optimum Conditions for the Application of Creosote-Pyridine Mixture.

Having determined the means of preventing disintegration, we next undertook to ascertain the optimum conditions for the removal of the incrusting matters without breaking down the fibre. Preliminary experiments to remove the lignone by treatment with creosote at 195° and at ordinary pressure showed that the amount of lignone removed in the course of 4-5 hours was practically negligible (Expt. 11, Table II). After 18 hours' treatment, the jute showed a loss of 22% in weight, but still contained 6.8% lignone (lignone content in raw jute being 19.69%) and was of apparently good tensile strength. Apparently, the cellulose complex was not absolutely unaffected by this prolonged treatment, as the above figures show. The progress in delignification was followed by means of the usual colour tests for lignocellulose and for cellulose with the help of microscope.

TABLE II.

Effect of time of treatment on delignification.

100 C.c. creosote for 1 gram of jute.

Temperature 195°; Pressure, ordinary.

Expt.	Time (hrs.)	Loss in wt. of jute. (%)	Lignone content. (%)	Tensile strength.
11	4	5.0	14.6	Good.
12	10	12.0	...	Good.
13	18	22.0	6.8	Good.

The following experiments represent attempts to reduce the time of treatment and to secure more effective delignification first by regulating temperature and pressure and secondly by the use of suitable catalyser.

From the following table (Table III) it will be noted that maximum delignification was obtained at a temperature of 193-195° and a pressure of 28-30 atmos. in the course of 4 hours without serious injury to the fibre. This may be contrasted with the results of Experiment 11 (Table II) where only slight delignification was obtained at ordinary pressure and at the same temperature (193-195°). Further increase in pressure with consequent rise in temperature resulted in diminishing the strength of the fibre.

It will be observed from Expts. 14 and 15 that delignification increased with rise in temperature. Further increase in temperature however affected the fibre adversely. In applying high pressure and temperature the use of pyridine was found necessary to prevent disintegration.

TABLE III.

Effect of temperature and pressure on delignification.

Time of treatment—4 hours.

Expt.	Temp. C.	Press. (atmos).	Creosote (c.c) for 1 gm. jute.	% of Pyrid- in creosote.	Loss in wt. %	Lignone content. %	Tensile strength.
14	160	1	100	60	2
15	195	1	100	...	5	14.6	Good
16	170	18	50	20	...	12.75	Good
17	180	22	50	20	14.3	9.7	Good
18	195	28-30	50	20	24.4	4.2	Fair
19	205	35	50	20	25.5	3.8	Bad

The use of hydrochloric acid and of halogens as catalyser have been investigated by different authors. In the case of jute, the use of hydrochloric acid could not be taken into consideration, owing to its hydrolysing action on cellulose. As recommended by Hillmer, iodine, the mildest of the halogens, was chosen for investigation. The application of creosote mixed with varying percentages of iodine showed increased loss in the weight of the fibre with increase in the amount of iodine (Expts. 20-22, Table IV). The fibre became brittle at the same time, owing to the action of hydriodic acid on cellulose. The action of iodine was apparently chemical, the cellulose complex having been seriously affected. To neutralise the action of hydriodic acid, pyridine was added to the mixture of creosote-iodine and experiments were carried on under optimum conditions of temperature and pressure. But it will be noted (Expt. 24 & 25) that the addition of small amounts of iodine did not help delignification. The use of substances which more or less attack cellulose as catalysers suggests that their function is to remove cellulose from the ligno-cellulose complex thus exposing lignone to the action of the solvent.

It has been mentioned that pyridine at high temperature and pressure attacks the cellulose complex to a considerable extent. Pyridine may therefore be expected to behave as a catalyser similar to halogen and halogen acids. From the results of the Expts. 3, 4, and 5 (Table I) this will be seen to be actually the case.

TABLE IV.

Effect of iodine as a catalyser.

Expt.	Vol. creosote (1 gm. jute).	Vol. pyridine.	Iodine (% on jute)	Time (hrs).	Temp. C	Press. (atmos.)	Loss in weight. %	Tensile strength.
20	75 c.c.	...	11.8	3½	145	10	15.1	Brittle
21	100 "	...	17.7	4	143	10	18.9	do.
22	125 "	...	20.3	3	143	10	20.6	do.
23	125 "	2	143	10	2.0	do.
24	50 "	30 c.c.	2	2	200	32	23.3	Fair
25	50 "	30 "	0	2	200	32	24.4	do

The influence of the time factor on delignification will be seen from the following table as also from Table II. From experiment 32, it will be noted that under optimum conditions of temperature, pressure and time the lignone content of raw jute can be reduced from 19.69% (Expt. 36) to 4.4% without seriously injuring the strength of the fibre.

TABLE V.

Progress of delignification with time of treatment.

Temperature 193-195°. Pressure 28-30 atmos.

Expt.	Time (hours.)	Vol. of creosote for 1 gm. of jute (c.c.)	Vol. of pyridine. (c.c.)	Loss in wt. of jute %	% Lignone content.	Tensile strength.
26	½	125	75	11
27	1¼	18.1
28	2	24.4
29	3	28.5
30	4	31.2
31	3	50	5	18.1	5.9	Good
32	4	23	4.4	Fair
33	5	26.3	2.9	Bad.

Analyses of Raw and Treated Jute.

Analysis of the jute cellulose obtained by the above treatment under optimum conditions (Expt. 32) was undertaken and the ash, moisture, lignone, and pentosan contents were determined. The figures may be compared with those obtained from an analysis of raw jute on the one hand and of jute cellulose obtained by chlorine treatment on the other. The results of the analyses of raw and treated jute are shown in the following table.

TABLE VI.

Analysis of Raw and Treated Jute.

Expt.	Raw jute.	Expt.	Treated jute.
34	Ash—0.68%	39	Ash—0.873%
35	Moisture—12.9%	40	Moisture—9.1%
36	Lignone—19.69%	41	Lignone—4.4%
37	Methyl no.—17.82%	42	Methyl no.—3.5%
38	Furfural—11.0% (pentosan)	43	Furfural—8.67% (pentosan).

It will be observed that the lignone matter has been substantially reduced by treatment with creosote-pyridine mixture but the pentosan content in the treated fibre is still high (8.67 per cent. furfural). This may be compared with the furfural content of 8.35 per cent.

which was found by Lehne and Scheppmann in jute cellulose obtained by Cross and Bevan's standard method of chlorine treatment (*Zeit. ang. Chem.*, 1925, 58, 95). This striking agreement in the furfural content suggests that the mechanism of the reaction of jute with phenols may be similar to that of chlorine (Cross and Bevan, "Cellulose," 1918, pp. 95, 135). Investigations in this direction have not, however, been completed.

Further Refining of the treated Fibre.

The furfural yielding complex (β -cellulose) in the raw jute cellulose obtained by the above treatment may be removed by two methods, namely (1) by heating with 5.6 per cent. NaOH solution, or (2) by treatment with 17.5 per cent. NaOH solution in the cold (Heuser and Bodeker, *Zeit. ang. Chem.*, 1921, 54, 461). Owing to the susceptibility of the fibre to concentrated alkali, only the first method was employed in these investigations. Addition of a small amount of phenol to the dilute alkali was found useful in improving the colour of the fibre to a certain extent. Analysis of this finally treated fibre gave the following results.

Expt.	
44	Lignone—2.5%
45	Furfural—4.09% (pentosan)

Evidently the alkali treatment serves to delignify jute further, in addition to the lowering of the furfural yielding complex. The fibre however retains its original colour and is apparently of good tensile strength. The bundle of the fibres breaks down into individual fibres of smaller diameter, owing to the removal of the gummy matter. Observed under the microscope it gives all the standard colour reactions of cellulose, as will be evident from the following table.

TABLE VII.

Reagent.	Cotton.	Raw jute.	Creosote-pyridine treated jute.	Finally refined jute.
Iodine solution	... Yellow	Brown	Yellow	Yellow
Zinc chloride-iodine	... Violet	Yellowish	Violet ¹	Violet ¹
Sulphuric acid-iodine	... Blue	Brown	Bluish	Bluish
Phloroglucine-HCl	... No coloration	Rose-red	Yellowish ²	Yellowish ²

¹ Development of colour takes a little time and is not so uniform as is the case with cotton.

² Apparently no change in colour, as the treated fibre is also yellowish.

Finally it may be observed that the production of cellulose fibre from jute lends support to the incrustation theory of the constitution of jute. It appears unlikely that the incrusting matters consist of the lignone-complex only but that the incrustation is formed by a lignone-cellulose complex, held together either by forces of chemical affinity (Cross and Bevan) or of surface energy (Wislicenus). That the incrusting matter is very firmly fixed to the cellulose is evident from the following considerations.

(a) While lignone, isolated by treatment with 42 % HCl (Willstätter), dissolves in phenols in a few minute (Hillmer, *Cellulose-chemie*, 1925, 6, 169) it requires several hours to effect the solution of the lignone-complex in jute.

(b) Cellulose attacking reagents, such as halogens, halogen acids and pyridine act as catalysers by exposing the incrusting matters to the action of solvents.

(c) From a comparison of the figures for loss in weight of the treated fibre and its lignone content it will be noted that a certain amount of cellulose is always affected in the attempt to remove the incrusting matter. The want of any fixed proportion between the amount of cellulose and lignone complexes removed suggests that the combination is more of a physical nature (Wislicenus) than of chemical.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Preparation of the Fibre.—The lowest portion (about 1 ft.) was rejected. The fibre was then freed from woody matters and separated as far as possible into individual fibres by mechanical means in order to get uniform results by creosote-pyridine treatment. It was further cut into small pieces and washed by means of soap solution (Pear's soap) in order to free it from dirt and adherent tissues. The difficulty of getting uniform quality of the fibre may further be reduced by loosening the bundle of jute by means of a short preliminary treatment with creosote-pyridine.

Creosote-pyridine Treatment.—Weighed quantity of the fibre prepared as above was taken in a small beaker with the necessary amounts of pyridine and creosote. The beaker was covered with blotting paper to prevent mechanical impurities and was then introduced in an electrical autoclave and placed on a piece of porcelain, pressure being exerted by means of vapours of rectified spirit. After the treatment, excess of creosote was removed by filtration through a Gooch's crucible and the fibre was washed thoroughly by means of

rectified spirit. It was then dried in an air oven at 105° and weighed. The follow data indicate the reduction in weight noted in the previous tables.

Expt.	Initial wt. of dry jute in gms.	Wt. after treatment (dry) in gms.	Reduction. %
1	0'4197	0'2939	30'0
2	0'7040	0'5226	25'6
3	0'8092	0'6104	24'5
4	1'4373	1'1060	23'0
5	0'9290	0'7670	17'4
6	0'4776	0'3800	20'4
7	1'1220	0'9236	17'6
8	0'3958	0'3308	16'4
9	1'6673	1'6460	1'0
10	0'8033	0'6278	21'8
11	0'8815	0'8364	5'1
12	0'7913	0'6948	12'1
13	0'9992	0'7832	21'9
14	0'3790	0'3715	2'0
15	0'8815	0'8364	5'1
17	0'8997	0'7200	14'1
18	0'8092	0'6104	24'5
20	0'3434	0'2914	15'1
21	0'2754	0'2232	18'9
22	0'1744	0'1383	20'6
23	0'3716	0'3662	1'4
24	0'3934	0'3017	23'3
25	0'4450	0'3362	24'4
26	0'2710	0'2408	11'1
27	0'3752	0'3051	18'6
28	0'4450	0'3362	24'4
29	0'3062	0'2188	28'5
30	0'3628	0'3495	31'2
31	0'9215	0'7544	18'1
32	1'4373	1'1060	23'0
33	0'6342	0'4670	26'3

Analysis of Jute.

(1) Moisture was estimated in the usual manner by drying at 105°. The amount in raw jute was found to vary with atmospheric humidity.

Expt	Wt. of jute (air dry).	Wt. of jute dried at 105°.	Moisture %
35	{ 1'5341 gms. 0'1934 gms.	{ 1'3240 gms. 0'1686 gms.	{ 13'1 12'7 } 12'9 (mean)
40	0'1348 gms.	0'1220 gms.	9'1

(2) Ash was estimated by igniting the jute in a platinum crucible.

Expt.	Wt. of dry jute.	Wt. of ash.	% of ash on dry jute.
31	3.6176 gms.	0.0042 gms.	0.68
39	0.2680 gms.	0.001 gms.	0.373

(3) Lignone in jute was estimated (a) indirectly by the determination of methyl number, and (b) directly by treatment with 42 % hydrochloric acid (Willstätter and Zechmeister, *Ber.*, 1913, **46**, 4201). The simple method of König and Becker of treatment with 72 % sulphuric acid was not followed as lignone is believed to be more or less affected by the acid of this concentration.

(a) Methyl number was determined by the method of Benedikt and Bamberger (*Monatsh.*, 1894, **15**, 509). By treatment with hydriodic acid according to the well known Zeisel method. As one gram of AgI corresponds to 0.06383 gm. of CH_3 , the methyl number (calculated on 1000 gms. of the fibre) is given by the following formula:—

$$\text{Methyl no.} = \frac{0.06383 \times N \times 1000}{A}$$

Where N is equal to the quantity of AgI (precipitate) in grams and A is equal to the quantity of fibre used (grams). The experimental data are given below.

Expt.	Wt. of dry fibre in gms.	Wt. of AgI in gms.	Methyl no. on dry fibre.
1	0.2139	0.0125	3.73
3	0.3181	0.0174	3.5
4	0.3452	0.0205	3.8
5	0.2719	0.0201	4.73
37	0.3076	0.0864	17.66
42	0.3181	0.0174	3.5

(b) *Estimation of lignone by treatment with highly concentrated HCl.*

Owing to the possibility of the methoxy groups being partly split off by the creosote treatment, determination of methyl number was given up in favour of the direct method of Willstätter and Zechmeister for the estimation of lignone. This method had the additional advantage of being less costly and required less attention. Owing to the difficulty of getting 42 % HCl we adopted the modification of Kroll (Schwalbe and Sieber, "Betriebs-Kontrolle in der Zellstoff and

Papier-Industrie", p. 102) and generated highly concentrated HCl by passing HCl gas, cooled in a condenser with ice water, in a mixture of jute and ordinary concentrated HCl, this mixture being at the same time cooled in ice. After allowing it to stand for 24 hours it was diluted to ten times its original volume with water, warmed and filtered through a Gooch's crucible and weighed after drying to constant weight. The cellulose was completely hydrolysed while the non-cellulose matter was left unaffected.

Expt.	Wt. dry jute in gms.	Wt. of lignone in gms.	% of lignone.
2	0'110	0'0042	3'8
3	0'1322	0'0056	4'2
4	0'1453	0'0062	4'4
5	0'2042	0'0196	6'5
6	0'1486	0'0148	10'0
7	0'2204	0'0120	5'4
11	0'1902	0'0278	14'6
13	0'2820	0'0194	6'8
15	0'1902	0'0278	14'6
16	0'1818	0'0234	12'76
17	0'2283	0'0222	9'7
18	0'1322	0'0056	4'2
19	0'1142	0'0044	3'8
31	0'1288	0'0076	5'9
32	0'1452	0'0062	4'4
33	0'1558	0'0046	2'9
36	0'4876	0'0421	19'69
41	0'1452	0'0062	4'4
44	0'1220	0'0030	2'5

(4) For the estimation of furfural yielding complex, the gravimetric method of Tollens and Bödener (*Zeit. für Landwirt.*, 1910, **58**, 232) was followed as more accurate than the modification of the same by Ling and Nanji (*Biochem. J.*, 1921, **15**, 466) suitable for volumetric estimation. The conditions recommended by Tollens and Bödener were strictly followed and the fibre was boiled with HCl of sp. gr. 1'06. the furfural in the distillate precipitated as phloroglucide and weighed after drying. The furfural content was estimated from the following formula:—

$$\text{Furfural} = (\text{Phloroglucide} + 0'001) \times 0'571.$$

Expt.	Wt. of dry jute (gms).	Wt. of ppt. gms.	Furfural % (on dry jute).
38	0'5206	0'1013	11'23
43	0'7137	0'1076	8'688
45	0'3685	0'0254	4'07

